

Tetraethyleneglycoldiacrylate as a selective extractant for Na⁺ using liquid-liquid extraction

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Abstract : The extraction study of alkali and alkaline earth metal ions was carried out from picrate, dinitrophenolate and orthonitrophenolate salts to ascertain the occurrence of complexation with podand in solution. Tetraethyleneglycoldiacrylate was immersed in various membranes viz. 1,2-dichloroethane, chloroform and carbontetrachloride. The podand is specific for Na⁺ in its pseudocyclic cavity. Onp⁻ is found as an efficient anion than others during extraction. These results could give an important suggestion to design the noncyclic ionophore with ion selectivity.

Keywords : Extraction, podand, selectivity, pseudocyclic.

Introduction

The present work has been undertaken to illustrate the versatility of tetraethyleneglycoldiacrylate as an ionophore immersed in various membranes. Membrane-based processes have attracted considerable attention as a valuable technology for many industries¹ in recent years. Solvent extraction is the simplest, rapid, selective and sensitive method of separation of metal ions.

The growth of applications, based on membrane processes mimics the active sites in naturally occurring biological molecules. These are very selective and sensitive sensors for analyzing the chemical composition of the environment or an organism through the determination of the concentration of the substances of interest. Chemical sensors could be used to detect individual molecules of a pollutant^{2,3}. The separation processes based on membrane technology represent a sophisticated route for the removal of soluble metal species from waste water⁴. An important unit operation of liquid-liquid extraction allows one to separate fluids based on different solutes being soluble to different degrees in different solvents.

Results and discussion

The extraction studies of alkali and alkaline earth metal cations have been carried out using synthetic tetraethyleneglycoldiacrylate (TEGDAC) as a podand. These results are summarized in Table 1.

The extraction processes are mainly controlled by complex formation and their stability for the particular set of experimental conditions in which extraction was carried out⁵. The metal salt concentration was varied from $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. But the optimum concentration of metal salts for extraction studies with ionophores was found $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Effect of cation :

The ionic diameter of metal cation and hole size of macroheterocycles are closely related and responsible for selective extraction⁶, while our results show that in case of noncyclic ligands, this specificity and selectivity do not depend on hole size but on preferred pseudocyclic conformation.

The observed trend for extraction of alkali metal ions is : Na⁺ > Ca²⁺ > K⁺ > Li⁺ ~ Mg²⁺ (Fig. 2).

Table 1. Amount of cation extracted into 1,2-dichloroethane, chloroform and carbontetrachloride membranes by TEGDAc after 4 h

Metal salts	Metal salt concentration = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, ionophore concentration = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$						Standard deviation (σ)
	1,2-Dichloroethane		Chloroform		Carbontetrachloride		
	Amount of cation extracted (ppm)	D_M	Amount of cation extracted (ppm)	D_M	Amount of cation extracted (ppm)	D_M	
Li.Pic	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.07	0.00
Li.Dnp	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Li.Onp	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Na.Pic	7.32	0.34	2.30	0.13	0.31	0.01	3.61
Na.Dnp	0.26	0.96	0.21	0.66	0.45	5.62	0.13
Na.Onp	9.96	1.44	10.72	1.75	5.72	0.51	2.69
K.Pic	2.12	0.16	0.85	0.06	0.32	0.02	0.93
K.Dnp	0.16	0.01	0.12	0.01	0.09	0.00	0.04
K.Onp	0.06	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.07	0.00	0.01
Mg(Pic) ₂	0.02	0.11	0.02	0.11	0.02	0.11	0.00
Mg(Dnp) ₂	0.01	0.09	0.01	0.09	0.01	0.09	0.00
Mg(Onp) ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Ca(Pic) ₂	0.08	0.02	0.24	0.06	0.26	0.07	0.10
Ca(Dnp) ₂	0.08	0.04	0.06	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.02
Ca(Onp) ₂	0.06	0.02	0.35	0.17	0.42	0.20	0.19

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of TEGDAc.

Fig. 2. Amount of cation extracted by TEGDAc from ortho-nitrophenolate salts in chloroform membrane.

Highest extracted amount of Na⁺ can be explained on its preferred size and charge density as well as conforma-

tional change of pseudocyclic cavity (Fig. 3) of ionophore due to ion-induced dipole interactions. It may be assumed that due to the smallest size of Li⁺ and Mg²⁺, charge density allows the solvation to a greater extent⁷ in aqueous solution and hence, pseudocyclic cavity of ligand

Fig. 3. Structural representation of the possible complexation between ionophore and metal ion in pseudocyclic cavity.

becomes improper towards its accommodation and complexation. Hence, both show minimum extraction. The amount of Ca²⁺ is more extracted than Mg²⁺ due to size and ion-dipole interaction. The overall results indicate that the binding of small ions (Li⁺ and Mg²⁺) leads to an unfavorable conformation of the ionophores characterized by interlinking site repulsions and deformation of the molecular frame. Hence, poor extraction of Li⁺ and negligible extraction of Mg²⁺ is observed due to highest heat of hydration.

Effect of anion :

Extraction ability of ionophore from aqueous solution to the organic phase is strongly influenced by the proper anion selection^{8,9}. The effect of anions i.e. Pic⁻ (picrate), Dnp⁻ (dinitrophenolate) and Onp⁻ (orthonitrophenolate) on the amount of alkali and alkaline earth metal cations extracted after 4 h was reported.

The mobility of cation-carrier-anion complex depends upon the characteristics of the anion and the extraction efficiency is sensitive to the presence of nitro groups. The trend for extraction of alkali and alkaline earth metal cations with ionophore is Onp⁻ > Pic⁻ > Dnp⁻ (Fig. 4) which is due to maximum hydrophobicity of Onp⁻. More extraction of metal ions with TEGDac from picrate salt is due to quite consistency of charge delocalisation in picrate ring.

Fig. 4. Effect of anions on amount of Na⁺ extracted by TEGDac in chloroform membrane.

Effect of solvent :

Chloroform has good extraction efficiency for sodium ion (Fig. 5) against others two (Table 1). The order of

Fig. 5. Effect of different bulk liquid membranes on amount of cation extracted by TEGDac using orthonitrophenolate salts.

extraction efficiency for Na⁺ using different solvents is as : chloroform > 1,2-dichloroethane > carbontetrachloride (Fig. 6). This result is according to the physico-chemical properties of the solvents such as polarity, viscosity and dielectric constant. This result may be attributed to the lower viscosity of chloroform ($\eta = 0.596$)

Fig. 6. Effect of different bulk liquid membranes on distribution ratio of cation extracted by TEGDac using orthonitrophenolate salts.

than 1,2-dichloroethane ($\eta = 0.887$) and carbontetrachloride ($\eta = 0.965$) which leads to increase the extraction efficiency in chloroform¹⁰. Carbontetrachloride has relatively thick water-free boundary layers that resist the

flux of both ions and ligand for complexation. Also acceptor number of carbontetrachloride (AN = 8.6) and 1,2-dichloroethane (AN = 16.7) is lower than chloroform (AN = 23.1), this reason increase in free energy of solvation of anion with cationic species in this solvent which can relate the ion extraction inversely to the negative free energy of solvation of Na-anion¹¹.

Effect of time :

Time dependence of cation extraction through liquid membrane designed under optimal experimental conditions (Fig. 7). The best extraction of cations was observed for four hours and no considerable change could be seen in after 2 h indicating that the time for attaining equilibrium is 2 h.

Fig. 7. Effect of time on % extraction of Na⁺ in chloroform from Onp⁻ salt.

Effect of stirring rate :

In order to explore the effect of stirring speed, the extraction experiments were performed at several different speeds. From the reported results, the convenient extraction of Na⁺ was happened at 250 rpm (Fig. 8). Reduction in extracted amount may be due to the decomplexation at higher speed.

Effect of ionophore concentration :

The extraction of Na⁺ from orthonitrophenolate salts have been carried out using different concentration of podand from $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$. But the

Fig. 8. Effect of stirring rate on % extraction of Na⁺ in chloroform from Onp⁻ salt.

optimum concentration of ligand for extraction studies with ionophores was found $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ (Fig. 9).

Experimental

Materials :

Li₂CO₃, Na₂CO₃, K₂CO₃, MgCO₃, CaCO₃ and C₂H₅OH were obtained from Rankem and were used without further purification. Picric acid, 2,4-dinitrophenol and 2-nitrophenol were obtained from Loba and

Fig. 9. Effect of ionophore concentration on % extraction of Na⁺ in chloroform from Onp⁻ salt.

Himedia. 1,2-Dichloroethane (DCE), chloroform and carbontetrachloride were obtained from Loba and Qualigens. All metal salts prepared have been described earlier¹².

Instrumentation :

Metal estimation of Na⁺, K⁺, Li⁺ and Ca²⁺ was carried out by digital flame photometer (Systronics 128) and of Mg²⁺ through atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 6300).

Procedure :

50 ml of 1.0 × 10⁻³ M aqueous metal salt [MX_n (Mⁿ⁺ = Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺; X⁻ = Pic⁻, Dnp⁻, Onp⁻)] solution was vigorously stirred with 50 ml of 1.0 × 10⁻³ M ionophore solution in CCl₄, CHCl₃ and C₂H₄Cl₂ in a small beaker using a magnetic stirrer (250 rpm) for liquid-liquid extraction studies¹³. The amount of cation extracted by the ionophore was found by determining its difference in aqueous phase before and after extraction. A blank experiment was also performed simultaneously with the same aqueous solution to determine the leakage of metal ion from aqueous to organic phase in absence of receptor. All measurements were performed in duplicate to check the reproducibility.

The equilibrium of metal-carrier complex in aqueous and organic phases is shown by the following equation :

Distribution ratio (D_M) was calculated as follows :

$$D_M = C_{org}/C_{aq}$$

Back extraction :

Back extraction studies were also carried out but no metal cation was detected in aqueous phase after back extraction which represents that ionophore does not show

back extraction with metal ions.

Conclusion

The results reported here lead to the conclusion that the noncyclic ionophore used has good extractability toward Na⁺ and it provides good potential for monitoring the Na⁺ in different fields. The study could be used to explore the possibility of designing a new specific carrier for metal ion selective electrodes.

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References

1. L. D. Nghiem, P. Mornane, I. D. Potter, J. M. Perera, R. W. Cattrall and S. D. Kolev, *J. Membr. Sci.*, 2006, **281**, 7.
2. A. Katrizky, A. Belykov, N. Dalal, O. V. Denisko and U. Maran, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **2**, 611.
3. P. Raizada and U. Sharma, *J. Chem.*, 2013, **2013**, 1.
4. L. Canet and P. Seta, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2001, **73**, 2039.
5. B. L. Lee, Y. Lee, Il Yoon, J. H. Jung, Ki-M Park and S. S. Lee, *Microchemical J.*, 2001, **68**, 241.
6. Y. Kobuke, K. Hanji, K. Horiguchi, M. Asada, Y. Nakayama and J. Furukawa, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 7414.
7. D. Mishra and U. Sharma, *Sep. Purif. Tech.*, 2001, **27**, 51.
8. U. Olsher, M. G. Hankins, Y. D. Kim and R. A. Bartsch, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **115**, 3370.
9. M. Shamsipur, S. Y. Kazemi, Azimi *et al.*, *Alexandria Engineering J.*, 2013, **52**, 123.
10. A. Nezhadali, M. Hakimi and M. Heydari, *E-J. Chem.*, 2008, **5**, 52.
11. S. Katsuta, F. Tsuchiya and Y. Takeda, *Talanta*, 2000, **51**, 637.
12. L. Lokwani, P. Ajwani and U. Sharma, *J. Sci., Islamic Rep. of Iran*, 2012, **23**, 123.
13. J. Tomar, M. Bhatnagar and U. Sharma, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 2007, **76**, 1.

